

INFLUENCE OF LAYER WAVINESS ON THE HYDROSTATIC RESPONSE OF THICK COMPOSITE CYLINDERS

M.W. Hyer
T.L. Brown

Department of Engineering Science and Mechanics
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
Blacksburg, VA 24061-0219

ABSTRACT

The influence of layer waviness on the stresses and pressure capacity of thick hydrostatically loaded cylinders is studied numerically by considering a single isolated circumferential wave in an otherwise perfect cylinder. The wave is characterized by its wave length λ and its wave amplitude δ . The cylinders are characterized by their radius to thickness ratio, R/H . The analysis is confined to a representative cross-section of cylinder, end effects being ignored. It is shown that relative to the perfect cylinder, waviness causes increased fiber-direction stress in the load-bearing circumferential layers, and interlaminar shear and tensile stresses, the latter stresses not being present in the perfect cylinder. The character of the stresses depends on where through the wall thickness waviness occurs. It is also shown that for reasonable levels of waviness, pressure capacities can be reduced by about a factor of two.

1. INTRODUCTION

Thick cylindrical submersible composite structures have been the subject of increased attention in the naval community. Many of the issues of importance in this application of composite materials have not been encountered in other arenas, for example, in the aerospace community. The thickness of the cylinder walls and the external hydrostatic loading environment are but two issues that are somewhat unique to naval applications. Cylinder walls hundreds of layers thick are envisioned for deep-sea structures. With many layers of material, there can be a number of defects which occur during fabrication. Layer wrinkles, resin rich regions, resin depleted regions, voids, and other anomalies can be expected. This study focuses on the influence of one anomaly, namely layer waviness. It would seem that the compressive nature of the hydrostatic loading, coupled with waviness in the load-bearing layers, would lead to reduced load capacity for the cylinders. Indeed, there appears to be a good correlation between the presence of layer waviness and premature failure in thick composite cylinders subjected to external hydrostatic pressure [1]. To explore this correlation, the present study focuses on the stresses associated with the presence of layer waviness in a hydrostatically loaded cylinder, and the influence of these stresses on failure.

2. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

To address the influence of layer waviness on the stresses and failure, a specific and somewhat idealized problem is considered. This idealization allows for an assessment of the importance of the parameters which characterize layer waviness. The particular problem studied is shown in fig. 1. The problem is that of a cylinder which, except for an isolated group of layers which exhibit circumferential waviness, is perfect. The cylinder is loaded by external hydrostatic pressure and is characterized by its mean radius R and its wall thickness H . A cross-sectional slice away from the ends of the cylinder is studied, it being assumed that the away from the ends the stresses, and hence strains, do not vary with the axial coordinate of the cylinder. With this model it is tacitly assumed that the waviness extends the full length of the cylinder.

The study here considers a laminate construction especially suited for hydrostatic loading, namely a construction with approximately twice as many layers with fibers in the circumferential direction as layers with fibers in the axial direction, a construction sometimes referred to as a 2:1 cross-ply construction. The specific stacking sequence studied is $[90/(90/0/90)_{17}]_S$, constituting 104 layers. Here 0° is the axial direction of the cylinder and 90° the circumferential direction. Cylinder geometries range from $R/H = 5$ to $R/H = 20$, the former geometry definitely being classified as a thick cylinder.

Details of the isolated wavy region are shown in fig. 1. The wavy region is assumed to encompass a group of 14 layers of the 104 layer laminate and is assumed to be symmetric to the left and right of the vertical centerline of fig. 1. In the circumferential direction the wavy region subtends an arc denoted by θ^{wave} . The quantity θ^{wave} is assumed to be large enough that at the right extreme of the wavy region the stresses have returned to the levels present in a perfect cylinder. The wave itself subtends an arc θ^* . A layer thickness is denoted as h and the midradius of the 14 layer group is denoted by R^* . The axial and circumferential layers are indicated in the figure. It is assumed that the waviness is due to the two central circumferential layers in the 14-layer group displacing outward an amount δ from the prescribed perfectly circular path in a cosinusoidal fashion. Layers inward and outward of these two central layers follow the waviness of the central layers. However, the variation of the other layers from being perfectly circular decreases to zero within seven layers inward and outward of the two central circumferential layers. The outward displacement of the two central layers results in resin richness inward of these layers, and resin depletion outward of these layers. This resin volume fraction variation results in a material property variation throughout the region of layer waviness. Equally important, with the wavy layers the orientation of the principal material directions varies with the circumferential coordinate, and from layer to layer. For a perfect cylinder the principal material axes are everywhere aligned with the radial and circumferential directions. With layer waviness, this is not the case. Rather the principal material directions vary within the wave, i.e., $\theta \leq \theta^*$. Outside the wave itself, $\theta > \theta^*$, the principal material axes are aligned with the radial and circumferential directions.

Two parameters describe the waviness: wave length λ and wave amplitude δ . Of course, the case $\delta \rightarrow 0$ reduces to the case of the perfect cylinder. Here normalized wavelength, $\bar{\lambda} = \lambda/h$, and normalized wave amplitude, $\bar{\delta} = \delta/h$, are used to characterize the wave, h being the thickness of one layer. The values of $\bar{\delta}$ studied here are $\bar{\delta} = 0$ (the perfect cylinder), 1, and 2. A value of $\bar{\lambda} = 10$ is used throughout, this representing a wave of moderate length. Of course, λ , R^* , and θ^* are related, as shown in fig. 1.

3. PROBLEM SOLUTION

With the region of layer waviness isolated, the philosophy used to obtain results was to assume that at sufficient distances away from the wave itself the response of the cylinder coincided with the response of a perfect cylinder, that solution being known [2] within the context of the theory of elasticity. Thus

just the wavy region needed to be studied, and the conditions to apply at the boundaries of the wavy region could be taken from the elasticity solution for the perfect case. To study the wavy region itself, the finite-element method was chosen, ABAQUS [3] being used exclusively, with PATRAN [4] also being used to prepare the finite-element models.

With many layers being studied, the issue of finite-element problem size became important, particularly in the context of parameter studies. Suffice it to say that two elements through the thickness of each layer, half-wall-thickness models, minimum values for the extent of the wavy region, θ^{wave} , and reduced integration were used to control problem size [5].

The material elastic properties used to represent a layer were taken to be:

$$E_1 = 132 \text{ GPa}; E_2 = 9.38 \text{ GPa}; E_3 = 9.24 \text{ GPa}$$

$$G_{12} = 5.52 \text{ GPa}; G_{23} = 3.45 \text{ GPa}, G_{13} = 5.52 \text{ GPa}$$

$$\nu_{12} = 0.279; \nu_{23} = 0.340; \nu_{13} = 0.279,$$

where the notation coincides with the convention of using a 1-2-3 principal material axis system to describe layer properties. A nonwavy layer was assumed to be 0.152 mm thick. It is important to realize that the above elastic properties are representative of a fiber volume fraction of 65%. Due to the resin richness and depletion associated with the formation of the wave, as mentioned before, the fiber volume fraction varies from point to point in the vicinity of the wavy layer. With the finite-element representation of the wavy region, the fiber volume fraction for each element was determined by comparing the volume of an element in the wavy region with the volume of a similar element in a perfect cylinder. Any difference in volume was assumed to be due to a deficiency or an excess of resin, it being assumed that all elements contained the same mass of fiber. Thus a fiber volume fraction could be computed that was assumed to be valid within the volume of each element. A simple modified rule-of-mixtures approach was then used to estimate the elastic properties for each element. The principal material directions within an element were assumed to coincide with the direction tangent to the midradial line of the element. It should be emphasized that with the ever-changing principal material directions the stresses of interest were the normal and shear stress which coincided with the direction of the interfaces of the curvilinear layers, σ_n and τ_{ns} . These will be referred to as the interlaminar normal and shear stresses, respectively. In addition, the stress in the tangential direction, σ_s , was of interest.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS - STRESSES

One important consequence of layer waviness is the generation of interlaminar shear and tensile stresses. With the hydrostatic loading of a perfect cylinder, interlaminar stresses are present in the form of compressive radial stresses. There are no shear stresses present in the perfect cylinder case. The introduction of layer waviness changes this picture. A second important consequence of layer waviness is the increase in fiber-direction compressive stresses. In the perfect cylinder there are fiber-direction compressive stresses. This is the primary reaction to the hydrostatic loading. However, waviness in the layers seriously increases these stresses. To follow is a discussion of the stresses caused by layer waviness. The particular case chosen for discussion is a cylinder with $R/H = 20$, a wave amplitude 2 times the layer thickness, i.e., $\bar{\delta} = 2$, and a wave length 10 times a layer thickness, i.e., $\bar{\lambda} = 10$. To illustrate the influence of the radial position of the waviness on the stresses, the layer numbering scheme shown in fig. 2 is used. Figure 3 illustrates the variation of interlaminar shear stress with circumferential location within the wavy region. Shear stresses for waviness at the inner radius ($R^* = R - H/2 + 7h$) and with waviness at the outer radius ($R^* = R + H/2 - 7h$) and for two interface

locations, one just above the central circumferential layers having the maximum disturbance relative to being perfectly circular, and one just below those layers. As can be seen in fig. 3, the character of the shear stress distribution at each interface is, for the most part, independent of the radial location of the waviness, and independent of the interface. What is important to note is that the shear stress is about three times the level of the applied pressure, a significant stress concentration effect. The interface exhibiting the maximum shear stress is neither one of these two, however. For that interface the shear stress is about 4 times the level of the applied pressure.

The interlaminar normal stresses at the two radial positions and the two interface locations are illustrated in fig. 4. For this stress component there is a significant effect of the radial position of the waviness and interface location on the character of the stress. What is important to note is that for interface 8* - 9* with the wave at the inner radial position, and for interface 6* - 7* with the wave at the outer radial position, interlaminar tensile stresses are predicted. This despite the overall compressive nature of the problem. Considering the normalized scale of the figures, tensile stresses about equal to applied pressure are computed. The interlaminar tensile stresses are generated due to the eccentricity in the loading of the circumferential layers caused by the waviness. The compressive stresses in the circumferential layers cause the circumferential wavy layer to deform radially much like a beam-column with an imperfection when subjected to an axial load. The layers inward and outward of the central wavy layer experience radial stresses, again, much like an elastic foundation surrounding the imperfect beam-column.

The character of the tangential compressive stress can be better shown by examining its variation through the thickness of the wavy layer region. Using a normalized radial distance through the wall of the cylinder, ρ , the tangential stresses moving out the line of symmetry of the wavy region, i.e., the left end of the wavy region, are shown in fig. 5. The variations of the stress within the wave when it is located at the inner radius are shown. (Only the stresses through the inner half of the cylinder wall are shown.) As expected, the tangential stresses are high in the load-bearing circumferential layers and quite low in the axial layers. Very clear is the significant waviness-induced increase in the tangential stress in the load-bearing circumferential layers. While the nominal normalized level of tangential stress in these layers away from the wavy region is about -30, stresses about twice that level are computed within the wavy region. The increase in stress in the wavy region is less when the wave is at the outer radial location, approximately 10% less.

5. NUMERICAL RESULTS - FAILURE PREDICTIONS

With the character of the stresses described, attention now turns to the influence of these stresses on failure. The maximum stress failure criterion is used. Of the various modes of failure, four modes, fiber-direction compression, interlaminar tension, interlaminar compression, and interlaminar shear, were considered as relevant. The fiber-direction strength, X_c , the interlaminar tensile strength, Z_t , the interlaminar compression strength, Z_c , and the interlaminar shear strength, S , are taken to be

$$X_c = 1241 \text{ MPa}; Z_t = 51.7 \text{ MPa}; Z_c = 207 \text{ MPa}; S = 93.1 \text{ MPa}.$$

To study failure, the pressure to cause failure in each of the modes, that pressure being denoted as P_{cr} , is computed and compared to the pressure to cause failure in the perfect cylinder, that pressure being denoted as P_0 . A perfect cylinder is predicted to fail due to fiber-direction compression in the inner circumferential layer.

The most important effect that waviness has on failure is to increase the fiber-direction tangential stress in the circumferential layers to the level that failure occurs in these layers at pressures significantly lower than that to cause the same failure mode in the perfect cylinder. It is the large increase in

the tangential stresses seen in fig. 5 that are responsible for this. The degree of pressure capacity reduction depends on the cylinder geometry, R/H , and the wave amplitude, δ . The next most important effect on failure is the level of interlaminar shear stress that is generated by the presence of the wave. Whether the fiber-direction compression or the interlaminar shear is more important depends on cylinder geometry, and the location and amplitude of the waviness. The failure pressure ratio, P_{cr}/P_o , as a function wave amplitude for different cylinder geometries and for waviness at the inner radius and at the outer radius, is shown in Figure 6. The pressures corresponding to the fiber-direction compression and interlaminar shear failure modes are shown on the figure. As can be seen, for the majority of the range of the parameters, the fiber compression mode is prevalent. Pressure reductions are higher when the waviness is located near the inner radius, and for larger values of R/H . The failure pressure ratio decreases monotonically with increasing wave amplitude. Interestingly enough, with the waviness at the outer radial location and for $R/H = 10$ and 20 , the interlaminar shear failure mode becomes more important than the fiber-direction compression mode as δ approaches 2. For δ greater than about 1.75, the interlaminar shear failure mode dominates. The key point to be made regarding fig. 6 is that due to layer waviness, pressure reductions of about a factor of two are a reality.

6. CLOSURE

Discussed has been the influence of layer waviness in the load-bearing circumferential layers on the stresses and subsequent failure in a hydrostatically loaded cross-ply cylinder. A very specific problem has been formulated and numerical results obtained. Despite the specificity, the important ingredients of waviness have been included in the problem. Variable fiber orientation, variable fiber volume fraction, and inner and outer radial location of the waviness are considered. It was shown that layer waviness causes a substantial increase in the fiber-direction stresses. Interlaminar shear stress, not present in the perfect cylinder, reach substantial levels in the wavy cylinder. In addition, interlaminar tensile stresses are present at some locations within the wavy layer region. Finally, it was demonstrated that waviness can lead to substantial reductions of pressure capacity.

7. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors wish to express their appreciation to the Office of Naval Research for financial support of the work discussed, the support coming under Grant N00014-90-J-1688. Appreciation to the Carderock Division of the Naval Warfare Center through Contract N0016791M7134 is also greatly appreciated.

8. REFERENCES

- 1 - Garala, H.J., 1989, "Structural Evaluation of 8 Inch Diameter Graphite-Epoxy Composite Cylinders Subjected to External Hydrostatic Compressive Loading," David Taylor Research Center Report DTRC - 89/016, Bethesda, MD.
- 2 - Hyer, M.W., 1988, "Hydrostatic Response of Thick Laminated Composite Cylinders," *J. Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, vol. 7, July, pp. 321-340.
- 3 - ABAQUS, 1987, Hibbit, Karlsson, and Sorenson, Inc. Providence, RI.
- 4 - PATRAN, 1989, PATRAN Division of PDA Engineering, Costa Mesa, CA, 1989.
- 5 - Brown, T.L. and Hyer, M.W., 1992, "Influence of Layer Waviness on the Hydrostatic Response of Thick Composite Cylinders," Virginia Tech Center for Composite Materials and Structures Report, CCMS-92-21, Blacksburg, VA

Figure 1. Problem considered and definition of parameters.

Figure 2. Layer numbering scheme.

Figure 3. Variation of interlaminar shear stress, τ_{ns} , with circumferential coordinate, $R/H=20$, $\bar{\delta}=2$, $\bar{\lambda}=10$.

Figure 4. Variation of interlaminar normal stress, σ_n , with circumferential coordinate, $R/H=20$, $\bar{\delta}=2$, $\bar{\lambda}=10$.

Wave located at inner radius.

Figure 5. Variation of tangential stress, σ_s , with radial coordinate, $R/H=20$, $\bar{\delta}=2$, $\bar{\lambda}=10$.

Figure 6. Failure pressure ratios.